

THE IMPORTANCE OF MENTAL ACTIVITY IN ADAPTATION TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The article examines the characteristics of the educational activity of primary school students. It begins with introducing primary school students to the process of teaching, the main components of educational activity: educational issues, educational situations, educational activities, control and evaluation. Assessment of the qualities of adaptation of primary school students to education, the role of mental abilities of students and the psychological analysis of the results of the collected research work are presented.

Key words: primary school students, educational activity, teaching process, main components of educational activity, adaptation to education.

Introduction

School education changes a child's lifestyle, social status, place in the class community and family environment. That is, play activities in the pre-school period alternate with study activities, which instills a sense of responsibility in the student. In this case, the content of primary education is inextricably linked with the student's interest in acquiring knowledge and the feeling of satisfaction from the result of his mental work. From this point of view, it is necessary to regularly monitor the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students, and to form the ability to use them in life, to fill the gaps in the knowledge of students in a timely manner, to create conditions for the regular development of the intellectual potential of talented students, to encourage students to work in cooperation with adults. interest in teaching, enriching pedagogical approaches and experiences aimed at protecting and strengthening their health, developing a plan of pedagogical activities outside the classroom, regular use of modern pedagogical technologies and the most advanced achievements of pedagogy in the process of education, establishing cooperation between teachers and parents , implies the implementation of tasks such as the use of modern methods in the retraining of primary school teachers and regular improvement of their qualifications. Today, in the concept of primary education, the goals and tasks of this system are clearly defined, and the identification and development of the hidden possibilities of the child's mind and thinking prepares children of junior school age not only to successfully master the learning material of new opportunities from the first period of education, but also to solve life problems.

increases his interest in learning and educational process. Specific tasks related to this issue are reflected in the following:

1. Reading, learning, application of acquired knowledge and formation of skills in elementary school students;
2. To strengthen the desire for highly developed cognitive process and cognitive activity among primary school students.

Therefore, it is clear from the above tasks that the formation of interest and inclinations of primary school students in educational activities, as well as increasing their aspirations, is one of the important factors, and taking into account the individual and psychological characteristics of the student in this process is its basis, that is, it discovers the essence of primary education. Without such an approach, it is difficult to improve the quality and efficiency of primary education.

In this regard, in order to form the interest of primary school students in educational activities, the quality of education will be increased as a result of promoting the integration of primary education content into the educational process, introducing new innovations, and effective use of information and communication technologies. When preparing primary school students for the educational process, taking into account the personal individual-psychological characteristics of students forms the pedagogical-psychological basis of their involvement in the educational process, and forms a sense of self-confidence in them. The student's will is seen in the conscious braking of his mental processes by the demands of the situation, especially in suppressing unnecessary emotions. Sometimes a child's behavior makes a teacher legitimately angry. However, in such a situation, the teacher should behave and be calm.

The success of the educational process largely depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills and interest. F. N. Gonobolin says that some mental processes and characteristics of the student form such a complex of qualities characteristic of the teacher that it is no exaggeration to call it pedagogical ability.

Pedagogical-psychological impact methodology consists of a system of tools used to organize children's socially useful activities in a pedagogically appropriate manner. These tools are aimed at the personality of the student, stimulate children's behavior, turn their difficult and complex tasks into a source of joy, creative pleasure, personal interests of each student. Science, whatever it is, does not create its methods out of nothing, it does not invent them. He selects from life the real factors of people's behavior, those that meet the tasks of organizing the children's life in a pedagogically-psychologically appropriate way,

and uses it as methods of pedagogical-psychological influence in educational and educational work.

The content of primary school education is inextricably linked with the student's interest in acquiring knowledge, satisfaction with the result of his intellectual work. This feeling occurs with the teacher's encouragement and forms the student's inclination, desire and enthusiasm to work more effectively. The sense of pride and confidence in one's own strength that has arisen in a child serves to acquire knowledge and develop skills. The process of teaching children of primary school age begins with the introduction of the main components of educational activities: educational issues, educational situations, educational activities, control and evaluation. In this regard, it is very important that all subject activities are carried out in conditions conducive to mental development. Learning of the student's educational activity is carried out in the process of solving the system of educational problems. At the beginning of the study, students of primary school age do not know how to independently set and solve educational problems. This task is initially performed by the teacher. Gradually, the students themselves begin to acquire the necessary skills and abilities to set and solve educational problems. This is an important stage in the formation of independent educational activity. Separation of educational issues creates certain difficulties for elementary school students. Therefore, at the end of each lesson, the teacher should take time to determine how his students understood the meaning of completing certain tasks.

First of all, it should be emphasized that the level of intellectual development of students is not determined only by the presence of knowledge or the ability to acquire theoretical or practical knowledge. The level of mental development of the student is the development of thought processes, the ability to distinguish between the important and the basic of the educational material, the ability to transfer the acquired knowledge or the acquired and mastered skills to other activities, the ability to apply various theoretical knowledge in practice, independent thinking. , is determined by several signs, such as the ability to draw conclusions. The opinions and opinions of elementary school students differ from opinions in terms of their content, form, and structure. This is due to the fact that the scope of their life experience is wider, and there are also differences in the way of revealing the essence of the problem, different approaches to things, and the difference depending on the characteristics of the age period. In order for students of I-IV grades to find the content of moral concepts, it is necessary to change the generalizing secondary signs of distinguishing the important signs of

each concept. The purpose of studying the psychological characteristics of primary school students in mental development is to identify and solve problems that hinder students' learning in the process of education.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is worth saying that a teacher must have good psychological knowledge in order to understand the inner world of a student. This is the ability of the student to be interested in the lesson, to be able to explain educational materials, to be able to correctly assess the student's knowledge, to have a positive educational effect on children, to be able to organize the work of a team of students and to lead them, to have the manners typical of pedagogues, to be able to deal with each student individually. Only then will he be able to involve students in the learning process.

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